
CIVIL SOCIETY: SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL AND LEGAL PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT
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Civil society plays an important role in social development, but it faces various challenges. Socio-philosophical problems are related to understanding the essence of civil society, its values and purpose of existence.

Development challenges include citizen participation in decision-making, ensuring their rights and freedoms, and building democratic institutions. Legal problems relate to the legislative provision of guarantees of civil rights, the process of law enforcement and the fight against corruption. These aspects need to be addressed and addressed in order to ensure the sustainable development of civil society

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Globalization processes that have led to fundamental, qualitative changes in all spheres of public life - economic, political, social, spiritual - require a deep socio-philosophical understanding and analysis of modern ideas about the transforming social world. In this regard, the study of civil society, the disclosure of its universal characteristics, taking into account modern realities, becomes particularly relevant.

Civil society is based on the principles of civil freedom, democracy, equality and Human Rights. However, there are several socio-philosophical problems associated with its understanding. One of these problems is identifying the real essence of civil society and understanding its goals and objectives.

There are often contradictions in people's opinions about whether civil society can provide all members of society with equal opportunities and freedoms. Also, sometimes there are questions about how best to ensure the participation of citizens in decision-making and control over power in civil society.

Paying attention to the process of development of society, the scientific community sought to overcome undesirable behavior of people in various ways. First of all, I called on them to act socially useful, as well as to identify important philosophical and economic factors in the formation of Public Relations.

The most important condition for interaction in society is predictability in the actions and behavior of people, but if it is not possible to predict it, then such behavior leads to disorganization and discord of any society. To prevent this, communities create mechanisms of social control that should consolidate society, regulate the activities of its members and ensure social order, stability, development and progress [6, 58].

The results of a study of special literature indicate that at the moment there are quite a large number of works, in particular: Johnson R., Karas A., Kovalev O., Kondov K., Kolot A., Shandra B., etc. Modern socio-philosophical ideology continues to actively study the importance of philosophical and legal factors in public relations.

It is true that the economy as a sphere of material social relations is the foundation of all social life. It is she who holds on to all other spheres of people's activity - politics, culture, morality, and the spiritual sphere. The level of social, spiritual, and cultural status of society is entirely determined by the level of economic development. At the same time, the active role of morality in social development and its reverse impact on the sphere of economic relations have never been denied. In the classics of political economics (A. Smith, K. Marx, A. Marshall and others) there are many judgments about human behavior in the economy, the importance of the moral factor in economic life. So, Karl Marx emphasized: "... all human relations and functions, in whatever form and in whatever form they manifest themselves, affect material production and more or less determine it "[8, 479].

A person is a product of their own motives of behavior and aspirations, which change under the influence of socio-cultural factors. Each individual develops systems of satisfactory relationships with other members of society. Man is a creation of society and establishes norms and rules of behavior as a result of communication with other members of society. Each of us has its own system of relationships, which determines the nature of Life [1, 67].

Stimulation is a process of influencing the subject of activity, aimed at making adjustments to the motives of its actions. Some researchers identify the concepts of "incentive" and "motive", and define incentive as the objective basis of economic interests.

A motive is an internal conscious impulse, and a stimulus is a set of values (goods) that act as methods of directing the motive. Thus, the concepts of "motive" and "stimulus" are different in their meaning, but interrelated: the strength of the motive is defined as a function of the magnitude of the good (value); on the other hand, the good becomes a stimulus if it forms a motive [7,65].

Economics, law, religion, politics, science, art, and other resources should be focused on implementing

this basic condition. Otherwise, if the government cannot direct its resource to achieve the main goal – the formation of a person, this resource will work for the destruction of society [9, 32-36].

Various methods and approaches were used to find out the very essence of the relationship between the main elements of the system. After all, each system is characterized by the fact that it has its own purpose, performs a certain function (each system is structurally designed) – the functioning of any system is finally determined by a person.

O. Kovalev rightly noted "on the close connection between man and society", noting that even the meaning of the whole story lies in the self-realization of Man and society, which is a kind of natural and social organism. Therefore, the driving force of the progress of society is not only material and production values or the need for self-improvement of the individual through the application of spiritual values and principles of equality and justice, but also the growth and improvement of the entire natural and social organism, which in the process of historical development, manifesting itself through social conditions, becomes by improving the conditions of existence, increasing life expectancy, mixing and selecting everything that is the best among different ethnic groups and, ultimately, the moral climate, strives for endless improvement, this, together with its progress, inevitably leads to the progress of its members, who are harmoniously integrated into a single system [5, 5].

If progress in relation to visible things can be easily noticed, then progress in relation to a person, and especially his moral state, cannot be traced on the surface. So, in terms of life expectancy, we see obvious progress: if at the time of the primitive social system, the average life expectancy was about 30 years, then in our time, in highly developed countries, it reaches the limits of 70-80 years.

As for the question of moral progress, there are two mutually contradictory approaches, the essence of which is that in one case they hold the opinion about the existence of moral progress, and in the other – about its absence, and even more – about the existence of moral regression during the historical course. Contrary to this, we share the view that there is progress rather than regression in the course of human development. After all, we can say about the current society: it has already passed the stage of human slavery, cannibalism, destruction of prisoners, gladiatorial fights, the practice of public executions, where the death of another person and a criminal turned into another show of boring everyday life [2, 39].

It is possible to observe the mutual influence of the social environment of both those who commit crimes and victims of crime today. It is known that the most criminogenic areas are always mostly inhabited by the poorest segments of the population, however, the victimization index – depending on social status – is as follows: workers account for 57.4 %, employees – 31% and collective farmers – 11.6 %. Regarding education, the highest level of victimization is observed among people with primary and incomplete secondary educa-

tion – 53.7%, as well as among those who are completely without education – 46.3 % [4, 39]. The level of victimization in Ukraine continues to be quite high.

Given the current time, it is necessary to assume that the above data still to a certain extent do not reflect the full structure of crimes that arise for certain reasons/without reasons or with the condition of socio-economic, psychological, political reasons.

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Most modern interpretations of the essence of civil society allow us to state that it is a human community that is formed and developed in Democratic states and is represented by a set of non — state relations (economic, social, political, ethnic, spiritual, cultural, confessional, legal, informational, organizational, etc.) and a network of voluntarily created non-state structures in various spheres of life — associations, organizations, unions, associations, clubs, centers, foundations, etc.

Considering civil society as a certain self — regulating social system, and the main component of which is "people-relations", it is advisable to distinguish the following characteristics: goals, principles and results. The goal of civil society is to achieve freedom — the condition and method of self-existence of a person as an active and full-fledged member of the community, "equal among equals", able to formulate value orientations and exercise their diverse interests according to the norms and rules established in society. As for the Civil Society of Modern Ukraine, its goal is to protect the inalienable rights and freedoms of the individual, to ensure its natural and social needs and interests, which, accordingly, correlates with the constitutionally proclaimed main goal of an independent democratic Ukrainian state. The most essential principles of civil society have developed historically and are formulated by scientists as its general ideas: first, economic freedom, diversity of ownership forms and market relations; secondly, the unconditional recognition and protection of natural human and civil rights, which implies equality of all before the law; thirdly, openness and self-regulation; fourthly, the development of democracy as a political ideal and mechanism of life of this system; fifth, the existence (development) of the rule of law, which is based on the idea of the rule of law, the principles of separation and interaction of branches of government and non-interference of the state in private life [10, 439].

In the end, the result of the functioning of civil society is, on the one hand, the development and complication of various social relations and ties — economic, social, spiritual — cultural, informational, political and legal (on the border with the "field" of the state), etc., and on the other — the improvement of the person himself, the formation of his equal and responsible participant in this community, the development of the creative and professional potential of a person who is ready to fulfill his duties and respect for the rights of others. According to Kant, a person should create everything on his own and be responsible for what is created [3, 339].

Thus, socio-philosophical and legal factors in the development of civil society include ideas about individual freedom, civil rights and obligations, equality before the law and Public Justice. These concepts help shape the values of society, promote civic engagement and interaction between people. Mechanisms of interaction between civil society and the state include the conclusion of social contracts, participation of citizens in decision-making through referendums and public hearings, as well as civil society mechanisms, such as non-governmental organizations that make demands on the authorities and monitor their activities. In general, the philosophical principles of civil society contribute to building an open and democratic society where citizens have the opportunity to influence important decisions and ensure that their rights are respected.

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